

Uploading Research Materials to Zenodo

This tutorial provides practical guidance for students in the Master in Information Science (MCI) who need to upload dissertation-related materials in the [MCI community on Zenodo](#). While the [accompanying FAQ](#) explains the main principles, requirements, and recommendations for sharing research data, this tutorial focuses specifically on the steps involved in uploading to Zenodo.

The tutorial is intended to support students throughout the submission process, from account creation and access to the community, to file upload, metadata completion, and final submission for curator review.

The community curator is João Aguiar Castro (joao.a.castro@inesctec.pt). The curator reviews uploads to the community, checks whether they meet the required quality standards, verifies the consistency and completeness of the metadata, and approves or rejects submissions as necessary.

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1. Before you begin

Before starting the submission process, make sure that:

- you have created a Zenodo account;
- you have been granted permission to upload materials to the MCI community;
- the files you intend to upload are final or sufficiently stable for sharing;
- the material has been organized clearly and is ready to be described in Zenodo.

If your upload includes datasets or other materials that require explanation for interpretation or reuse, prepare a README file in advance.

2. Access the MCI community on Zenodo

Go to the MCI community page on Zenodo and sign in with your account. If you already have permission to upload, you will be able to begin a new submission from the community page.

If you do not yet have permission, you must first request access from the community managers or curators.

3. Start a new upload

To begin the process, select the option to create a new upload (green button below).

Zenodo will open a submission form where you can add files and complete the metadata describing your upload. At this stage, the upload remains in draft form. This means that you may still revise the information, replace files, or add complementary documents before submitting it for review.

4. Upload the files

Upload the main file or files that you wish to share. The upload should normally correspond to one main resource type. Complementary materials may be included in the same upload when they directly support the main file.

Examples of complementary files include:

- a README file accompanying a dataset;
- appendices or supporting documentation;
- additional files required to understand or reuse the material.

If the files correspond to different and independent outputs, they should be submitted as separate uploads.

When naming files, use clear and meaningful filenames so that their contents can be easily identified.

5. Complete the metadata

After uploading the files, complete the metadata form carefully. This step is essential because the metadata allow the material to be identified, understood, retrieved, and reused.

The metadata should preferably be completed in English. Fill in all required fields and complete additional fields whenever they add useful information about the upload. Particular attention should be paid to the following.

5.1 Basic information

DOI

If the material already has a DOI, retain it. If not, Zenodo may generate one during the upload process. The DOI will only become usable after the material is published. If the upload draft is deleted, the identifier will be lost, meaning that a different DOI will need to be obtained.

The screenshot shows a blue header bar with the text "Basic information" and a downward arrow. Below the header, the text "Digital Object Identifier*" is followed by the question "Do you already have a DOI for this upload?". There are two radio button options: "Yes, I already have one" (which is selected) and "No, I need one". Below the radio buttons is a text input field with the placeholder text "Copy/paste your existing DOI here...". At the bottom of the form section, there is a small note: "A DOI allows your upload to be easily and unambiguously cited. Example: 10.1234/foo.bar".

Resource type

Select the resource type that best matches the main material in the upload.

Title

Provide a clear and informative title that accurately reflects the material being uploaded. In addition to the main title, translated titles, subtitles, alternative titles, and other variants may also be added using the “Add Titles” option located below the title field. It is also possible to specify the language in which these titles are presented.

Publication Date

The publication date is automatically filled in with the date on which the upload is being made. If the material has already been published previously, this date should be changed to the original publication date. The format Year–Month–Day is recommended, in accordance with Zenodo’s platform guidelines.

Creators

To add a creator, click the Add Creator button located in this section.

 Creators*

 + Add creator

After clicking this button, you will be able to add the information of the creators of the material being uploaded. In this context, you may enter your first name and family name, as well as the respective identifiers if you have them. You may also indicate your role in the material. If the material has co-authors, they can be added by clicking the “Add Creator” button again and filling in their information.

Add creator

Person Organization

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Family name* Given names

Identifiers

Affiliations

Role

Creators will be listed in the order in which the information is entered, with the first being considered the main author and the others as co-authors. Information about the supervisor may also be added if they appear as a co-author of a specific material, such as in some scientific articles or posters.

Description

Although it is not a mandatory field, the description is essential to provide an overview of the uploaded material and to include key information that supports its understanding and development.

Some basic formatting can be applied to the description, such as the use of headings, bold or italic text, lists, paragraphs, and other simple formatting options. Additional descriptions may also be added to explain other aspects of the material and improve organisation, such as methodological details or technical information. Depending on the material being uploaded, the student should select the available options that best describe the upload.

Important information to include in the description may consist of a summary of the material, an explanation of the context and purpose for which it was created, the methods and tools used in its production, explanations of abbreviations, codes, or other details that may be essential for third parties to understand the material, and, when applicable, instructions for reusing the material.

Licences

Assigning a reuse licence to the uploaded material is essential to ensure compliance with the open science principles promoted by Zenodo. By default, the platform automatically assigns the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence, which allows the material to be shared and adapted, provided that appropriate credit is given to the creator and any changes made to the material are indicated.

Although this is the recommended licence, it may be changed by selecting the “Edit” button, if a different licence is more appropriate. Additional licences may also be added if the upload includes materials under different licensing conditions, for example, a software component and a publication, since Creative Commons licences are generally not recommended for software.

After editing or adding a new licence, you may choose from the various options provided by Zenodo, including recommended licences, licences intended for data, licences intended for software, or the full list of available licences.

Change standard license

Q

Recommended
All
Data
Software

- Apache License 2.0**
A permissive license whose main conditions require preservation of copyright and license notices. Contributors provide an express grant of patent rights. Licensed works, modifications, and larger works may be distributed under different terms and without source code.
- Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**
The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited.
- Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 International**
Permits almost any use subject to providing credit and license notice. Frequently used for media assets and educational materials. The most common license for Open Access scientific publications. Not recommended for software.
- Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal**
CC0 waives copyright interest in a work you've created and dedicates it to the world-wide public domain. Use CC0 to opt out of copyright entirely and ensure your work has the widest reach.
- GNU General Public License v3.0 or later**
Permissions of this strong copyleft license are conditioned on making available complete source code of licensed works and modifications, which include larger works using a licensed work, under the same license. Copyright and license notices must be preserved. Contributors provide an express grant of patent rights.
- MIT License**
A short and simple permissive license with conditions only requiring preservation of copyright and license notices. Licensed works, modifications, and larger works may be distributed under different terms and without source code.

« (1) »

Did not find your license? [Add a custom license.](#)

✕ Cancel
✓ Change license

If you wish to add a new custom licence, this may be done by selecting the “Add Custom” button and completing the corresponding information.

Add custom license

Title *

Description

Link

✕ Cancel
✓ Add license

It is recommended that the licence chosen should be consistent with open science principles, supporting the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of the uploaded materials.

5.2 Recommended information

To better describe the material and the upload being created, you should complete the information presented in the “Recommended information” section.

Contributors

To add contributors, click the “Add Contributor” button.

 Contributors

You can then add information about individuals or organisations that supported the production of the material, such as by providing access to information sources or assisting with the research process, but who are not directly responsible for the intellectual creation of the uploaded content.

When adding a contributor, it is important to indicate their role using the “Role” field. However, contributor roles are not taken into account when generating citations for the uploaded material.

Add contributor

Person Organization

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Family name

Given names

Identifiers
e.g. ORCID, ISNI or GND.

Affiliations
Search or create affiliation

Role*
Select role

Keywords and subjects

You should include relevant keywords to ensure that your material can be correctly retrieved within the platform. Zenodo provides a controlled vocabulary that helps improve the discoverability of uploaded materials. This vocabulary includes terms from the *European Science Vocabulary (EuroSciVoc)*, *Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)*, and the *General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus (GEMET)*.

If the desired term is not available in the controlled vocabulary, you may manually add the appropriate keyword.

 Keywords and subjects

Search for a subject by name

Language

You should assign the correct language of the uploaded material to ensure that users are aware of any potential language barriers when interpreting the data.

 Languages

Search for a language by name (e.g "eng", "fr" or "Polish")

Dates

Additional dates may be added to the material, specifying the type of date represented. For example, you may indicate the date on which the material was accepted, the date when the data were collected or created, or other relevant dates. The type of date can be selected from the drop-down list available in the “Type” field.

 Dates

Date *	Type *	Description
YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD		

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

Version

If the material being uploaded may have updated versions, such as datasets or software, the current version of the material should be indicated in the Version field.

 Version

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

5.3 Additional information

Zenodo also provides an “Additional information” section where further details about the uploaded material can be included. Although these fields are not always mandatory, completing them can improve the quality, traceability, and reuse of the uploaded material.

Funding information

The **Funding** section is used to indicate funding sources related to the project. This may include research grants, awards, scholarships, or other forms of financial support that contributed to the development of the work.

To add a funding source, click the “Add” button to search for funding information available on the platform. If the funding source is not listed, you may use the “Add Custom” button to enter the information manually.

Funding

 Awards/Grants

Add standard award/grant

- Consortium on improving access to integrated Sexual and Reproductive Health and Mental Health services among mobile populations. 222438
Wellcome Trust
- Vacation Scholarships 2018 - University of Edinburgh 213308
Wellcome Trust
- Understanding the child protection support system for online child sexual abuse in Switzerland: Perspectives of young people and professionals (OSAS - online sexual abuse support) 10902273
Swiss National Science Foundation
- Understanding the role of CpG islands in gene regulatory element function and transcription. 98024
Wellcome Trust
- Song of Contagion 281641
Wellcome Trust

« (1 2 3 4 5 ... 2000) »

Did not find your award/grant? [Add a custom award/grant.](#)

Add custom funding

Funder *

Additional information (optional)

Number	Title	URL
Award/Grant number	Award/Grant Title	Award/Grant URL

Alternative identifiers

Alternative identifiers may be used when the uploaded material has additional external identifiers. In the context of the dissertation project, this section may be used to reference external platforms related to the material, such as the **YouTube URL of the dissertation pitch**.

Alternate identifiers ▼

▣ Alternate identifiers

Identifier *	Scheme *
	<input type="text" value=""/> <input type="button" value="✕"/>

+

Related works

The **Related works** section allows you to indicate other materials that are relevant for understanding or reusing the uploaded material. This section can be used to connect different outputs of the same project, such as a dataset and a publication produced within the same research work.

When adding related works, you should specify the relationship between the materials and provide the corresponding identifier and resource type.

▼

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

▣ Related works

Relation [*]	Identifier [*]	Scheme [*]	Resource type	
Select relation...	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	✕

+ Add related work

References

If applicable, you may include references to sources used during the production of the material. Zenodo provides a field where references can be inserted following standard citation formats (e.g., APA or other commonly used referencing styles).

▼

▣ References

Reference string ^{*}

✕

+ Add reference

Software information

If the upload involves **software**, additional information should be provided about it. This may include:

- a link to the platform where the source code is available;
- the programming language used (for example Python, HTML, or XML);
- the development status of the software.

▼

🔗 Repository URL

URL or link where the code repository is hosted.

🔗 Programming language

e.g. Python ...

Repository's programming language.

♥ Development Status

Repository current status.

Publication information

If the material being uploaded has already been published elsewhere, details about the publication should be provided in the relevant fields.

For example:

- if the material is a **scientific article published in a journal**, the publication details should be added in the **“Journal”** section;
- if the material is part of a **book or book chapter**, the relevant information should be added in the **“Imprint”** section;
- if the upload relates to a **dissertation**, the academic institution and submission information may be included in the **“Thesis”** subsection.

Publishing information
▼

Journal

Title

Title of the journal in which the article was published

ISSN

International Standard Serial Number

Volume

Issue

Page range or article number

Imprint (Book, Chapter, or Report)

Book or report title

Title of the book or report which this upload is part of

ISBN

International Standard Book Number

Place

Place where the book or report was published

Pagination

Edition

The edition of the book

Thesis

Awarding university

Awarding department

Thesis type

The type of thesis (e.g. Masters, PhD, Engineers, Bachelors)

Submission date

Submission date in YYYY-MM-DD format.

Defense date

Defense date in YYYY-MM-DD format.

Conference information

If the uploaded material is associated with a **conference**, information about the event can be added in the **“Conference”** section.

Although this may not always occur during the dissertation project, this information may be added later if relevant, for example by creating a **new version of the upload** after the dissertation has been completed.

6. Add a README file when necessary

If the material cannot be easily understood on its own, include a README file. This is particularly important for datasets.

A README file should help future users understand:

- what the files contain;
- how the material was created;
- the meaning of variables, abbreviations, or codes;
- the structure of the files;
- how the material may be interpreted or reused.

The README should be written clearly and provide enough context for someone unfamiliar with the project.

Conference ▼

Title	<input type="text"/>	Acronym	<input type="text"/>
Place	<input type="text"/>	Dates	<input type="text" value="e.g. 21-22 November 2022"/>
<small>Location where the conference took place.</small>			
Session	<input type="text" value="e.g. VI"/>	Part	<input type="text" value="e.g. 1"/>
<small>Session within the conference.</small>		<small>Part within the session.</small>	
Website	<input type="text"/>		

7. Review access conditions

Before submitting the upload, review the visibility available in Zenodo. This is an important stage of the process and should be checked carefully before submission.

Zenodo does not allow the open sharing of materials that contain identifiable personal data. For security and privacy reasons, the repository offers different access options for uploaded materials, depending on the type of data included.

7.1 Public access

Public access is the default option for each upload. With this option, both the metadata and the uploaded materials are openly accessible to users of the platform without additional restrictions. This option is recommended for compliance with open science principles.

Visibility

Files only

Public Restricted

Public
The record and files are publicly accessible.

Options

Apply an embargo
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

7.2 Restricted access

Restricted access allows the upload to be visible to the public after validation, but the uploaded files are accessible only to specific users or users with the required permissions.

Users who wish to access the material may send a request to the student responsible for the upload, who may accept or reject the request. To grant access permissions to specific users, click the “Share” button on the upload page and select the most appropriate sharing options.

Visibility

Files only

Public Restricted

The files of this record are restricted.

Public with restricted files
The record is publicly accessible. The files can only be accessed by users specified in the permissions.

Options

Apply an embargo
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Share access

People Links Settings

People with access	Access	+ Add people
Beatriz Silva Universidade do Porto	Owner	

Short name for your link (optional).

Expiration date format: YYYY-MM-DD
Expiration date: YYYY-MM-DD or never if blank (optional).

Can preview drafts

Create a new link

People 1
Links 2
Settings

Allow authenticated users to request access to restricted files.

Allow non-authenticated users to request access to restricted files.

Enable users and guests to request access to your record's files. When access is requested by someone, you will get an e-mail asking for approval. After you approve a request, users will be granted access and guests will receive a secret link.

Accept conditions

Optional. Specify conditions under which you approve access. This message will be visible for any user when requesting access to this record.

Paragraph
B I (t) [Media] [Table] [List] [Text] [Link] [Undo] [Redo]

Advanced options

Link expiration

Never

✕ Cancel
✓ Save

7.3 Embargoed access

Embargoed access allows the materials to remain restricted until a specific date defined by the student. Until that date, the materials are accessible only to users with appropriate permissions. After the embargo period expires, the materials automatically become publicly accessible to users of the platform.

Visibility

Files only

Public

Restricted

The files of this record are restricted.

Embargoed (files-only)
The record is publicly accessible. On ??? the files will automatically be made publicly accessible. Until then, the files can only be accessed by users specified in the permissions.

Options

Apply an embargo Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Embargo until

YYYY-MM-DD
Format: YYYY-MM-DD

Embargo reason

Optionally, describe the reason for the embargo.

8. Submit the upload for review

Once the files and metadata have been completed, review the entire submission carefully before sending it for curator review. Confirm that:

FEUP - EDIFÍCIO I - SALA 012A | RUA DR. ROBERTO FRIAS | 4200-465 PORTO - PORTUGAL | TELEFONE +351 225 082 134 E-MAIL: MCI@FE.UP.PT

- the correct files have been uploaded;
- the upload corresponds to one main resource type;
- a README file has been included when needed;
- the metadata are complete and accurate;
- the description is sufficiently informative;
- the keywords are relevant;
- the visibility settings are appropriate;
- the licence has been checked;
- no openly shared file contains identifiable personal data;
- any useful note to the curator has been added.

It is recommended to contact the curator if it is necessary to clarify any additional aspect that is not included in the metadata provided.

Submit for review

⚠ Before requesting review, please read and check the following:

The 'Mestrado em Ciência da Informação' curators will have access to view and edit your upload's metadata and files.

If your upload is accepted by the community curators, it will be immediately published. Before that, you will still be able to modify metadata and files of this upload.

Message to curators (optional)

9. After submission

After submission, the curator will review the upload before it is approved for publication in the community.

If the curator identifies problems or missing information, you may be asked to revise the upload before publication. For this reason, it is important to provide clear metadata and sufficient documentation from the start.

Once approved and published, the upload becomes part of the MCI community on Zenodo.

10. Updating a published upload

After publication, the upload cannot simply be removed and replaced in the same way as a draft. If changes are needed, they should normally be made by creating a new version of the upload.

Updates may include:

- replacing or correcting files;

- improving metadata;
- changing permissions or visibility settings.

If deletion is necessary, Zenodo support may need to be contacted.